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2 **Influence of the β parameter of the Haverkamp model on the transient**
3 **soil water infiltration curve**
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ABSTRACT

Soil water infiltration can be described with the quasi-analytical Haverkamp et al. (1994) equation, defined by the hydraulic conductivity (K_s), sorptivity (S) and the β parameter. K_s and S are commonly estimated from the transient cumulative infiltration curve, using a constant β value. The objective of this work was to study the influence of β on the estimation of K_s and S . The study was first performed on synthetic 1-D infiltration curves generated at different infiltration times for loam sandy, loamy and silty soils, and next extrapolated to a 3-D loam synthetic soil and on 10 infiltrations curves measured on the field with a disc infiltrometer on different types of soils. The infiltration measurements lasted between 600 and 900 s. The results showed that, while early infiltration times (i.e. 100 s) promoted good estimations for S , longer infiltrations (i.e. 1.000s) were required to estimate accurately K_s . Only very long infiltration (i.e. 10.000 s) allowed defining the actual β value. A similar behaviour was observed for the 3-D infiltration measurements. Except for β , significant relationships ($R^2 = 0.99$) were obtained between the K_s and S of the three theoretical soils and the corresponding values calculated by optimizing the three hydraulic parameters on 2.000 s 1-D infiltration curves. The large confidence interval observed in β (between 0.3 and 2.0) resulted from the fact that β had a small effect on the infiltration curve. A significant relationship ($R^2 = 0.99$) was also obtained between the K_s and S optimized from the experimental curves using a $\beta = 1.1$ and the corresponding values obtained by simultaneous optimization of the three hydraulic parameters. These results demonstrated that S and K_s can be accurately estimated using a constant β and that downward infiltration is not an appropriate procedure to estimate β .

Keywords: Sorptivity, Hydraulic Conductivity; Water Retention Curve, Methods

1.- INTRODUCTION

47 The knowledge of water movement in the soil is of central importance in many research areas, such
48 as agronomy, civil engineering, hydrology and environmental sciences. Haverkamp et al. (1994)
49 developed a physical base three-dimensional infiltration model for disc infiltrometer derived from the
50 Richards equation. This equation was the sum of the 1-D infiltration curve, defined by the hydraulic
51 conductivity (K), sorptivity (S) and the β parameter, and an additional term depending on time, the disc
52 radius, the initial and final soil volumetric water contents, the S value and a proportionality constant
53 (γ). The complete Haverkamp et al. (1994) model, together with its approximate expansions, have been
54 successfully applied in many different infiltration researches (Pueyo et al., 2013; Moret-Fernández et
55 al., 2013; Latorre et al., 2015; Di Prima et al., 2016; among others). In particular, the approximate
56 expansions for the transient and steady states are used in many methods designed for the hydraulic
57 characterization of soil (e.g., Lassabatere et al., 2006, Yilmaz et al., 2010; Bagarello et al., 2014).

58 Sorptivity describes the capacity of a porous medium to absorb or desorb liquid (Philip, 1957). It is
59 a function of the diffusivity and the initial and final volumetric water content (θ) (Parlange et al., 1975).
60 K , which measures the soil ability to transmit water when it is submitted to a hydraulic gradient, is
61 function of the hydraulic head or the soil water content (Dane and Hopmans, 2002). β is an integral
62 shape constant that depends on the soil diffusivity, the hydraulic conductivity function, and the initial
63 and final volumetric water contents (Haverkamp et al., 2006). Within the applicability of the model, β
64 ranges between 0.3 and 1.7, suitable from sandy to silty soil textures, as estimated by Lassabatere et al.
65 (2009), using numerically generated data. Recent works demonstrated that β is related to the soil
66 textural characteristics (Moret-Fernández et al., 2017). γ is a correction factor for the use of simplified
67 geometry of the wetting front below disc infiltrometer to derive the additional term for 3D infiltration
68 (Haverkamp et al., 1994). Although Fuentes et al. (1992) proposed physically based equations to define
69 parameters β and γ , Lassabatere et al. (2009) observed that their formulations provided values
70 contrasting with actual and plausible values. These same authors found that γ was dependent on the

71 soil type, with values ranging between 0.75 and 1. More recently, Latorre et al. (2015) compared the
72 complete Haverkamp et al. (1994) formulation with synthetic infiltration curves generated with
73 HDYRUS-2D, and observed that consistent K and S values were obtained from inverse analysis of
74 these cumulative infiltration curves when constant β and γ values were employed. In this case, the
75 constant γ value of 0.75 proposed by Haverkamp et al. (1994) will be used. The study of this parameter
76 will be the subject of further studies, and the proposed study focuses on the role played by parameter
77 β , with the analysis of its impact on 1D cumulative infiltration curves or 3D infiltration curves
78 computed considering parameter γ fixed at 0.75. Further research will focus on the addition of
79 parameter γ as potentially variable and optimizable.

80 Infiltration-based methods are valuable techniques to measure the soil hydraulic properties. Among
81 the different infiltration-instruments, the tension disc infiltrometer is a worldwide used tool for in situ
82 estimation of soil hydraulic properties in the vadose zone. This instrument consists of a base disc
83 jointed to a graduated water-supply reservoir and a bubble tower to impose a negative pressure head
84 (h) at the base disc (Perroux and White, 1988). The soil hydraulic properties are commonly calculated
85 from the cumulative water infiltration curves, which are measured from the drop in the water level of
86 the reservoir tower. Correct measurements of the infiltration curve require the membrane of the disc
87 base to be completely in contact with the soil surface. To achieve this, a contact sand layer is placed
88 on the soil surface. Several procedures have been developed to estimate K and S from tension disc
89 infiltrometer measurements, including the analysis of (i) the steady-state data (Smettem and Clothier,
90 1989; Ankeny et al., 1991), (ii) the early-medium transient state curve (e.g. Vandervaere et al., 2000),
91 (iii) the combination of transient and steady states (Lassabatere et al., 2006); and (iv) the whole
92 cumulative infiltration curve (Latorre et al., 2015). Compared to the steady-state water flow methods,
93 the transient water flow procedures, that require shorter experiments and ensure smaller sampled soil
94 volumes and more homogeneous initial water distribution, lead to better estimates and better
95 representativeness of the local hydraulic properties (Angulo-Jaramillo et al., 2000). On the other hand,

96 comparing different transient methods, Latorre et al. (2015) demonstrated that the use of the complete
 97 quasi-analytical Haverkamp et al. (1994) equation gives more robust results than the methods based on
 98 the simplified Haverkamp et al. (1994) formulation. However, in both cases a constant β value is
 99 employed. Although Haverkamp et al. (1994) and Latorre et al. (2015) supported this assumption,
 100 several studies have proved that the parameter β was not necessarily constant and could vary with the
 101 type of soil (Moret-Fernández and Latorre, 2017, Lassabatere et al., 2009).

102 Given the above-described studies, which show that the effect of β on the estimation of downward
 103 infiltration is not clear enough, the objective of this paper is to deepen the study of the Haverkamp
 104 equation by analysing the influence of β on the downward infiltration curve and related consequences
 105 when inverting the downward infiltration curves to derive soil hydraulic parameters. Because of its
 106 greater simplicity, the analysis was first applied on synthetic 1-D infiltration curves, and next
 107 extrapolated to 3-D synthetic and experimental infiltration curves measured with a disc infiltrometer.

108

109 **2. METHOD AND MATERIALS**

110 **2.1. Theory**

111 The 1-D cumulative infiltration, I_{1D} , is described by the quasi-exact equation, derived by Haverkamp
 112 et al. (1994) from the Richards equation:

$$113 \quad \frac{2(K_0 - K_i)^2}{S_0^2} t = \frac{2}{1 - \beta} \frac{(K_0 - K_i)(I_{1D} - K_i t)}{S_0^2} - \frac{1}{1 - \beta} \cdot \ln \left[\frac{1}{\beta} \exp(2\beta(K_0 - K_i)(I_{1D} - K_i t) / S_0^2) + \frac{\beta - 1}{\beta} \right] \quad (1)$$

114 where t is time (T), K_0 and K_i ($L T^{-1}$) are the hydraulic conductivity values corresponding to the final,
 115 θ_0 , and initial, θ_i , volumetric water content ($L^{-3} L^{-3}$), respectively; S_0 ($L T^{-0.5}$) is the sorptivity for θ_0 (L^3
 116 L^{-3}); and β is defined as an integral shape parameter.

117 The 3-D cumulative infiltration, I_{3D} , from a surface disc source can be expressed by the 1-D equation
 118 plus an additional time linear term (Smettem et al., 1994):

119
$$I_{3D} = I_{1D} + \frac{\gamma S_0^2}{R_D(\theta_0 - \theta_i)} t \quad (2)$$

120 where R_D (L) is the radius of the disc and γ is the proportionality constant. Substituting Eq. (2) into Eq.
 121 (1), an implicit 3-D infiltration equation valid for the entire time range is obtained (Haverkamp et al.,
 122 1994)

123
$$\frac{2(K_0 - K_i)^2}{S_0^2} t = \frac{2}{1 - \beta} \frac{(K_0 - K_i) \left[I_{3D} - K_i t - \gamma S_0^2 / ((\theta_0 - \theta_i) R_D) t \right]}{S_0^2} -$$

 124
$$\frac{1}{1 - \beta} \ln \left[\frac{1}{\beta} \exp \left(2\beta (K_0 - K_i) \left[I_{3D} - K_i t - \gamma S_0^2 / ((\theta_0 - \theta_i) R_D) t \right] / S_0^2 \right) + \frac{\beta - 1}{\beta} \right] \quad (3)$$

125
 126 According to Lassabatere et al. (2009), the values of γ and β range from 0.75 to 1 and from 0.3 to
 127 1.7, respectively, suitable from sandy to silty soils. These authors derived such values by fitting
 128 equations (1) and (2) to numerically generated data. The respective initial and boundary conditions for
 129 infiltration process are

130
$$\begin{aligned} z = 0, t > 0, \theta = \theta_s \\ |z| \leq 0, t = 0, \theta = \theta_i \\ |z| \rightarrow -\infty, t > 0, \theta = \theta_i \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

131 where z is a vertical coordinate (L) positive upward and θ_i and θ_s ($L^3 L^{-3}$) are the initial and saturated
 132 volumetric water contents. Depending on the sign of z , downward ($z < 0$) or upward ($z > 0$) infiltration
 133 can be described. Fuentes et al. (1992) designed the following estimate for the β shape coefficient :

134
$$\beta = 2 - 2 \frac{\int_{\theta_i}^{\theta_0} (K - K_i / K_0 - K_i) (\theta_0 - \theta_i / \theta - \theta_i) D(\theta) d\theta}{\int_{\theta_i}^{\theta_0} D(\theta) d\theta} \quad (5)$$

135 where $D(\theta)$ ($L^2 T^{-1}$) is the diffusivity defined by Klute (1952) as

136

$$D(\theta) = K(\theta) \frac{d\theta}{dz} \tag{6}$$

137

and h is the matric component of soil water potential (L).

138

Studying water infiltration into a homogeneous with a uniform initial water content and infinite

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length horizontal soil column, Parlange (1975) obtained the following estimate for the soil sorptivity:

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$$S_e = \frac{\theta(h) - \theta_r}{\theta_s - \theta_r} \tag{7}$$

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On the other hand, the unsaturated soil hydraulic properties can be described according to the van

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Genuchten-Mualem model (Mualem, 1976; van Genuchten, 1980):

143

$$S_e(h) = \frac{\theta(h) - \theta_r}{\theta_s - \theta_r} = \frac{1}{(1 + |\alpha h|^n)^m} \tag{8}$$

144

$$K(\theta) = K_s S_e^{0.5} \left[1 - \left(1 - S_e^{1/m} \right)^m \right]^2 \tag{9}$$

145

where S_e is the effective water content, θ_r ($L^3 L^{-3}$) denotes the residual volumetric water content and α

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(L^{-1}), n , and $m = (1 - 1/n)$ are empirical parameters. Combining Eq. (6), (8) and (9), the diffusivity can be

147

defined as (van Genuchten, 1980):

148

$$D(S_e) = \frac{(1-m)K_s}{cm(\theta_s - \theta_r)} S_e^{1/2 - 1/m} \left[\left(1 - S_e^{1/m} \right)^{-m} + \left(1 - S_e^{1/m} \right)^m - 2 \right] \tag{10}$$

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2.2. Estimate of S , β and K from the inverse analysis of an infiltration curve

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Latorre et al. (2015) provided a numerical procedure to solve Eq.(1) and Eq.(3). Since γ is not studied

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in this work, a constant value equal to 0.75 has been considered (Haverkamp et al., 1994). The S , K

153

and β parameters are estimated by minimizing an objective function, Q , that represents the difference

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between Eq. (1) or (3) and the experimental cumulative downward infiltration curve:

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$$Q = \int_0^z \left(\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial q}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial z} \frac{dz}{dt} \right)^2 dz \tag{11}$$

156 where N is the number of measured (I, t) values. To simplify the study, the existence and the
157 uniqueness of the solution was studied by analysing the Q error maps for the K_s - β , S - β and S - K_s planes,
158 where the third parameter of each 2D-map was fixed to the remaining theoretical value (Table 1). A
159 global optimization (Pardalos and Romeijn, 2002) for different infiltration periods was employed. The
160 response surfaces were calculated on a rectangular grid with K_s from 0.001 to 0.1 mm s⁻¹, S from 0.1
161 to 1.5 and β ranging from 0.3 to 1.7. An additional analysis of the K_s , S and β with respect to the final
162 time of infiltration was also performed. This consisted on calculating the t - K_s , t - S and t - β error maps
163 using in each plane the theoretical remaining parameters and t ranging from 0 to the end of the
164 infiltration.

165 In order estimate S , K and β from the inverse analysis of an infiltration curve, a global optimization
166 approach over three dimensions of Q (K_s , S and β) was developed. This optimization process presents
167 the following steps : :

- 168 1. The measured data (recorded every 1 s) was resampled to 100 points. To this end, an iterative
169 procedure that determines the error of the regression line for each three consecutive points and
170 removes the central point with lower error, was applied.
- 171 2. A three steps global optimization on (S , K_s and β) was performed: the first one used a
172 (400x50x50) grid, the second one a (100x100x100) grid centered on the optimal S value and
173 a third one with a (1x400x400) grid on the optimized S . The initial grid used for K_s , S and β
174 ranged from 0.001 to 0.1 mm s⁻¹, 0.1 to 1.5 mm s^{-0.5} and 0.3 to 1.7, respectively.
- 175 3. Within the global search, the simulated curves with a total cumulative infiltration larger/lower
176 than ± 5 mm around the experimental value were discarded. This allowed a faster screening of
177 the optimal K_s , S and β .

178

179 **2.3. Numerical experiments**

180 The theoretical downward infiltration data was numerically generated with the HYDRUS-1D and 3-
181 D software (Simunek et al., 2006). Loam sandy, loamy and silty soils (Carsel and Parrish, 1988) were
182 used. The values of the hydraulic parameters (α , n , K_s , β and S) of the theoretical soils are summarised
183 in Table 1. For 1-D infiltration analysis, a 30 cm-high soil column was discretized using a 1-D mesh
184 of 1000 cells. The minimum time step used in the simulations was 10^{-4} s. The initial pressure head of
185 the homogeneous and isotropic column was -1.66×10^6 cm, which according to Munkholm and Kay
186 (2002) it corresponds to air-dry conditions. The tension at the base of the soil column was 0 cm.
187 Atmospheric conditions with a maximal tension of 0 cm was imposed at the top boundary. This
188 condition does not allow water to build up on the surface, preventing water overpressures on the soil
189 surface. Since the experimental measurements are relatively fast (between some minutes to 1 h), a null
190 evaporation rate was considered.

191 The 3-D infiltration experiments were simulated using HYDRUS-3D model (Simunek et al., 1999),
192 considering only a loam soil (Table 1). The soil volume was discretized as a cylinder (radius of 25 cm
193 and depth of 25 cm), covering the axisymmetric plane with a 2-D rectangular mesh of 100×900 cells.
194 The vertical cell size was variable to obtain a finer mesh near the surface, ranging from 0.003 cm on
195 the top to 0.3 cm on the bottom. Maximum and minimum time steps were fixed at 0.05 s and 10^{-4} s,
196 respectively. An initial pressure head of -1.66×10^6 cm was also selected. This values ensured low
197 initial water contents, θ_i , with $\theta_i < \theta_s$, where θ_s stands for the saturated water content. The initial soil
198 water content was close to the residual water content. A base disc infiltrometer of 10 cm radius was
199 represented as a constant pressure head boundary on the corresponding cells, the rest of the soil surface
200 was treated as atmospheric boundary with no flux. A null pressure head was considered as bottom and
201 lateral boundaries, which is supposed valid if the water does not reach these regions. Because Eq. (1)
202 the considers the soil as column of infinite length, only the infiltration curves between time zero and
203 the time just before the wetting front arrives to the bottom of the soil column were considered. It was

204 then considered the modeled cumulative infiltration at surface would have been the same for other
205 boundary conditions.. The simulations run up to 50 mm water infiltration.

206 Under hypothetical perfect downward infiltration curves, the three hydraulic parameters can be
207 optimized up to a very small error (i.e, 10^{-6} mm). However, as reported by Latorre et al. (2015), under
208 experimental conditions the measured infiltration curve is subjected to experimental uncertainties (such
209 as the accuracy of water level measurement). The uncertainty for the experimental disc infiltrometer
210 was 0.05 mm, which means the lowest contour line should correspond to an uncertainty of 0.05 mm
211 for the distance between the fitted and target cumulative infiltrations. Therefore, a well-shaped contour
212 line corresponding to 0.05 mm confirms that there should be only one unique solution for applied
213 method while the contour line with a valley shape confirms that multiple solutions can occur and,
214 consequently, it is not possible to determine some of the hydraulic properties.

215

216 **2.4. Experimental measurements**

217 Because the difficulties to measure in situ 1-D downward infiltrations, the experimental validation
218 was performed on 3-D disc infiltrometer measurements. The infiltrometer measurements were done in
219 10 agricultural fields located in the North Monegros county (Huesca, NE Spain). The climate is semi-
220 arid (14.5°C average annual temperature, 413 mm of annual average rainfall) (Comín and Williams
221 1994). The study area was mostly cultivated by maize, alfalfa, barley, wheat applying sparkling
222 irrigation and rice through flood irrigation in this quite flat area. Additional measurements on small
223 natural shrubland areas were also performed. Textural, chemical, and management characteristics of
224 the studied soils are summarized in Table 2.

225 The soil dry bulk density (ρ_b) was determined using the core method (Grossman and Reinsch, 2002)
226 with core of 50 mm in diameter and 50 mm in height. To determine the dry weight of the soil, the
227 samples were dried at 105°C for 24 h. One replication, was performed per sampling site. This sampling
228 also made it possible to determine the initial volumetric water content (θ) needed in Eq. (3). The 3-D

229 transient cumulative infiltration curves were measured with a Perroux and White (1988) model tension
230 disc infiltrometer. The diameter of applied disc and internal diameter of the water reservoir tower were
231 100 and 34 mm, respectively. To ensure a good contact between the soil surface and the disc base, a
232 thin layer (< 1 cm thick) of commercial sand (80–160 μm grain size and an air-entry value between -1
233 and -1.5 kPa) with the same diameter as the disc base, was placed between disc and soil surface. All
234 infiltration measurements were taken on the soil surface crust, on areas cleared of large clods and crop
235 residue. A null pressure head on the base disc was selected. The water infiltration was automatically
236 monitored with ± 35.2 cm differential pressure transducer (Microswitch, Honeywell) applying an
237 scanning time interval of 1 s. Infiltration measurements continued for 500 to 900 s. A soil sample was
238 taken to estimate the saturated gravimetric water content (W) when infiltration measurement was
239 ended. θ_s was then calculated as the product between W and the previously calculated ρ_b . A total of 10
240 cumulative infiltration curves were recorded. The effect of the contact sand layer on the analysis of the
241 cumulative infiltration curve was omitted using the Latorre et al. (2015) procedure. The applied method
242 considers the effect of sand layer as a delay in time and volume before water infiltrates into the soil.
243 Then, the effect of the contact layer can be removed by finding the sand infiltration time (and its
244 corresponding water volume), that corresponds to the time required for water to fill in the sand, and
245 shifting the experimental data to the origin (in time and water volume). Because β is directly related to
246 the soil textural properties (Moret-Fernández and Latorre, 2017;), 0.6 for sand up to 1.7 for silt soils
247 leading to an average β value of 1.1 was employed in the inverse analysis of the experimental
248 infiltration curves.

249

250 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

251 The values of S and β of the theoretical soils were numerically calculated with Eqs. (7) and (10),
252 and Eqs. (5) and (10), respectively (Table 1). Because its greater simplicity, the effect of β on downward
253 infiltration processes was first analysed on 1-D curves (Eq. 1). The error maps in the β - K_s , S - β and S -

254 K_s planes showed that early infiltration times (i.e. 100 s) promoted good approaches of S but not of K_s
255 and β (Fig. 1). The valley shapes observed in the β - K_s , S - β and S - K_s planes indicated that different
256 combinations of K_s and β resulted in similar accuracy of infiltration curve fits (Fig. 1). However, the
257 S - K_s error map progressively changed when longer infiltration times were applied. In this case, 1,000
258 s of infiltration were enough to obtain a unique and well-defined minimum in the S - K_s plane (Fig. 1),
259 which accuracy improved with increasing infiltration times. For the remaining S - β and β - K_s planes,
260 however, quasi-vertical and horizontal contour lines were observed (Fig. 1). This revealed that a large
261 range of β gave similar infiltration curves, and hence S and K_s values, which indicates that β is
262 independent of S and K_s . Only very large infiltration times (i.e. 10,000 s) allowed defining the actual
263 β value. The small influence of β during the first stages of infiltration could be related to the fact that
264 wetting fronts and infiltration fluxes are more related to strong water pressure gradients and less related
265 to soil texture and thus parameter β (Moret-Fernández and Latorre, 2017) taking part in the process.
266 However, as time increases, the water pressure head reduces and the infiltration state changes involving
267 more the parameter β (Fig. 1). The analysis of the time-evolution of S , β and K showed that S and K_s
268 were well defined in early and medium infiltration times, respectively. The estimation of β needed
269 much longer time (Fig. 2). Although this simple analysis does not allow describing the interaction
270 between the three hydraulic parameters, it gives a fast idea of the influence of time on the optimized
271 K_s , S and β .

272 Except for β , significant relationships with slope close to unity and small confidence intervals were
273 obtained between the theoretical K_s and S and the corresponding values calculated from a global
274 optimization over the three parameters (K_s , S and β) on a 1-D infiltration curve of 2,000 s (Fig. 3). The
275 large confidence interval observed in β (between 0.3 and 2.0) indicates that a large range of β gives
276 very similar infiltration curves and thus leads to comparable fits. This would indicate that β had a small
277 effect on the downward infiltration curve and on the estimation of S and K_s . Thus, as reported by

278 Haverkamp et al. (1994) and Latorre et al. (2015), any constant value of parameter β value can be
279 used.

280 Because β does not affect the right term of the 3-D infiltration model (Eq. 2), the β - K_s , S - β and S -
281 K_s contour maps calculated for a 3-D infiltration on a loam soil were similar to those observed in 1-D
282 (Fig. 4). These results agree with Latorre et al. (2015), who observed that K_s and S could be accurately
283 estimated from the inverse analysis of a 3-D downward infiltration curve when a constant β value was
284 employed.

285 As an example, Figure 5 shows the experimental and the corresponding best fit infiltration curves
286 (after removing the contact sand layer effect), and the β - K_s , S - β and S - K_s error maps calculated for the
287 soil number 5 (Table 2). Similar to that observed for the theoretical curves, only the S - K_s error map
288 showed a unique and well-defined minimum. In this case, 800 s of infiltration were enough to optimize
289 these parameters. However, the quasi-vertical and horizontal contour lines obtained in the S - β and β -
290 K_s planes indicated that a large range of β resulted in very similar S and K_s values. Thus, the great
291 uncertainty obtained in β (Table 3) reveals that, within the range of field measurements, downward
292 infiltration is not an appropriate technique to estimate this parameter. Finally, the significant
293 relationship between K_s and S calculated from experimental infiltrations using a fixed $\beta = 1.1$ and those
294 obtained by simultaneous optimization of the three hydraulic parameters (after removing the contact
295 sand layer effect) (Fig. 6) suggests that under in situ infiltration measurements, K_s and S can be
296 satisfactorily estimated using a constant β .

297

298 CONCLUSIONS

299 This work analyzes the influence of β on the cumulative infiltration curve, and the consequences on
300 the accuracy of fits and estimates for K_s and S . The analysis was performed on synthetic downward
301 infiltration generated for different times and for loam sandy, loamy and silty soils. Next the analysis

302 was again applied on a 3-D synthetic loam curve and on experimental infiltration curves measured with
303 a 50 mm radius disc infiltrometer. While early infiltration (i.e. 100 s) only promoted good approaches
304 of S (Fig. 1), long infiltration times (i.e. 1,000 s) were required to estimate K_s . Only very long
305 infiltrations (i.e. 10,000 s) allowed defining the actual β value. On the other hand, the theoretical
306 analysis of 1-D curves indicates that β had a small effect on the downward infiltration curve, and hence,
307 on the estimation of S and K_s . Similar behaviour was observed in the theoretical 3-D and experimental
308 infiltration curves. Within the range of field measurements (i.e. 1000-2000 s), downward infiltration is
309 not an appropriate procedure to estimate β . However, the saturated hydraulic conductivity and soil
310 sorptivity can be accurately estimated using a constant β value.

311

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Figure captions

397

398

399 **Figure 1.** Error maps for the S - β , S - K_s and β - K_s combinations calculated for a theoretical loamy soil
400 at 100, 1000 and 10000 s of 1-D downward infiltration. The third parameter of each error map
401 was fixed at the theoretical value. Blue symbol denotes the theoretical S , β and K values. Red
402 contour line corresponds to $Q = 0.05$ mm.

403

404 **Figure 2.** Response surfaces for the t - S , t - K_s and t - β combinations calculated for a 1-D cumulative
405 downward infiltration curve simulated on a theoretical loamy soil. The remaining parameters of
406 each error map correspond to the theoretical values. Thick red line indicates the experimental
407 uncertainty contour line (0.05 mm).

408

409 **Figure 3.** Relationship between the theoretical K_s and S of loamy sandy, loamy and silty soils (Table
410 1) and the corresponding values calculated from a global optimization over the three parameters
411 (K_s , S and β) on a 1-D infiltration curve of 2.000 s. Vertical lines denote de confidence intervals
412 within the 0.05 mm contour line of the error maps (Fig. 1).

413

414 **Figure 4.** Error maps for the S - β , S - K and β - K combinations calculated for a theoretical loamy soil at
415 5700 s of 3-D downward infiltration. The third parameter of each error map corresponds to the
416 theoretical value. Blue symbol denotes the theoretical S , β and K values.

417

418 **Figure 5.** Experimental and the best fitting infiltration curve, and error maps for the S - β , S - K and β - K
419 planes calculated from the 3-D downward infiltration measured in the experimental soil #5. The

420 third parameter of each error map was fixed at the theoretical value. Blue symbol denotes the
421 optimized S , β and K values.

422 **Figure 6.** Relationship between K_s and S calculated from experimental infiltrations using a fixed $\beta =$
423 1.1 and those obtained by optimizing the three hydraulic parameters.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 5.

Table 1. Values of initial (θ_i), saturated (θ_s) and residual (θ_r) water content, α and n parameters of the van Genuchten (1980) water retention curve, hydraulic conductivity (K_s) and sorptivity (S) (Eq. 8) at saturation and shape factor (β) (Eq. 3) of the theoretical loamy sand, loam and silt soils.

	θ_i	θ_s	θ_r	α	n	K_s	S	β
	cm^3	cm^{-3}		cm^{-1}		mm s^{-1}	$\text{mm s}^{-0.5}$	
<i>Loamy sand</i>	0.057	0.41	0.057	0.124	2.28	$4.05 \cdot 10^{-2}$	1.025	0.78
<i>Loam</i>	0.078	0.43	0.078	0.036	1.56	$2.88 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.367	1.27
<i>Silt</i>	0.034	0.46	0.034	0.016	1.37	$6.93 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.238	1.50

Table 2. Soil CaCO₃, organic carbon (OC) and initial (θ_i) and saturated (θ_s) volumetric water contents, soil bulk density, ρ_b , soil texture and soil management characteristics of the studied soils.

Soil number	CaCO ₃	OC	θ_i	θ_s	ρ_b	Sand	Silt	Clay	Soil and use management
	g kg ⁻¹		m ³ m ⁻³			%			
1	185	6.33	0.1	0.37	1.45	83.73	14.27	2.00	Agricultural (under fallow in a cereal-fallow rotation with conventional tillage)
2	244	9.88	0.22	0.37	1.45	50.44	36.29	13.28	Agricultural (rainfed cereal cropping under no tillage)
3	308	9.74	0.12	0.50	1.64	47.92	36.77	15.31	Agricultural (rainfed cereal cropping under conventional tillage)
4	269	5.34	0.06	0.43	1.46	55.47	32.08	12.45	Agricultural (irrigated cereal cropping under conventional tillage)
5	350	12.77	0.15	0.467	1.50	48.25	35.95	15.80	Agricultural (rainfed cereal cropping under no tillage)
6	208	10.26	0.06	0.54	1.41	50.73	37.68	11.59	Agricultural (irrigated legume crop under conventional tillage)
7	265	18.50	0.05	0.54	1.27	44.48	39.18	16.34	Agricultural (irrigated legume crop under conventional tillage)
8	237	13.18	0.02	0.54	1.17	55.60	31.69	12.71	Agricultural (rainfed cereal cropping under no tillage)
9	419	36.68	0.06	0.55	0.82	46.67	33.31	20.02	Natural (typical Mediterranean shrubland)
10	257	15.23	0.26	0.55	1.35	25.87	49.79	24.34	Agricultural (irrigated cereal cropping under conventional tillage)

Table 3. Hydraulic conductivity (K_s), sorptivity (S) and β factor estimated from the inverse analysis of experimental 3-D cumulative infiltration curves using the Latorre et al. (2015) procedure (with a fixed β) and optimizing the three hydraulic parameters. Within brackets, the confidence interval within the 0.05 mm error contour line

Soil	K_s and S optimization (Latorre et al., 2015)			K_s , S and β optimization		
	K_s mm s ⁻¹	S mm s ^{-0.5}	β	K_s mm s ⁻¹	S mm s ^{-0.5}	β
1	1.1 10 ⁻² [7.7 10 ⁻³ , 4.4 10 ⁻²]	0.42 [0.42, 0.43]	1.1	7.6 10 ⁻³ [7.5 10 ⁻³ , 1.9 10 ⁻²]	0.41 [0.41, 0.42]	0.18 [0.18, 1.89]
2	3.2 10 ⁻² [3.2 10 ⁻² , 3.3 10 ⁻²]	0.25 [0.24, 0.26]	1.1	3.3 10 ⁻² [3.3 10 ⁻² , 3.4 10 ⁻²]	0.22 [0.20, 0.23]	0.76 [0.73, 1.31]
3	5.6 10 ⁻³ [5.1 10 ⁻³ , 6.5 10 ⁻³]	0.08 [0.08, 0.10]	1.1	5.6 10 ⁻³ [5.0 10 ⁻³ , 6.3 10 ⁻³]	0.08 [0.07, 0.09]	0.97 [0.30, 2.00]
4	1.7 10 ⁻³ [1.0 10 ⁻³ , 2.4 10 ⁻³]	0.07 [0.06, 0.08]	1.1	1.2 10 ⁻³ [1.1 10 ⁻³ , 2.7 10 ⁻³]	0.07 [0.06, 0.07]	0.18 [0.18, 2.00]
5	9.0 10 ⁻³ [0.9 10 ⁻³ , 1.0 10 ⁻³]	0.15 [0.15, 0.16]	1.1	9.0 10 ⁻³ [0.9 10 ⁻³ , 1.0 10 ⁻³]	0.16 [0.16, 0.17]	2.11 [1.57, 2.11]
6	2.1 10 ⁻³ [1.4 10 ⁻³ , 2.9 10 ⁻³]	0.12 [0.12, 0.13]	1.1	1.8 10 ⁻³ [1.2 10 ⁻³ , 3.6 10 ⁻³]	0.12 [0.12, 0.13]	0.69 [0.30, 2.00]
7	1.8 10 ⁻² [1.8 10 ⁻² , 1.9 10 ⁻²]	0.31 [0.31, 0.32]	1.1	1.8 10 ⁻² [1.8 10 ⁻² , 1.9 10 ⁻²]	0.29 [0.29, 0.30]	0.74 [0.46, 0.92]
8	7.9 10 ⁻³ [7.9 10 ⁻³ , 8.7 10 ⁻³]	0.20 [0.19, 0.21]	1.1	8.3 10 ⁻³ [7.1 10 ⁻³ , 9.4 10 ⁻³]	0.17 [0.17, 0.18]	0.64 [0.30, 1.37]
9	1.3 10 ⁻² [1.3 10 ⁻² , 1.4 10 ⁻²]	0.29 [0.28, 0.31]	1.1	1.4 10 ⁻² [1.1 10 ⁻² , 1.4 10 ⁻²]	0.27 [0.28, 0.29]	0.85 [0.30, 1.18]
10	6.9 10 ⁻³ [6.5 10 ⁻³ , 8.2 10 ⁻³]	0.14 [0.13, 0.16]	1.1	7.2 10 ⁻³ [6.7 10 ⁻³ , 8.4 10 ⁻³]	0.14 [0.13, 0.15]	0.41 [0.30, 1.33]